

***THE INFLUENCE OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND MINDFULNESS
TOWARDS WORK ENGAGEMENT IN WORKING'S MOTHERS IN
GARMENT INDUSTRY OF PT. BRA.***

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Abstract

The no of working's mothers is kept on increasing time to time. Work Engagement on garment industry of workforce still having problem nowadays with various reason. The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of work life-balance and mindfulness to work engagement of working mothers in the garment company PT. BRA, Bantul, Yogyakarta. The subjects of this study were 553 working's mothers with criteria minimum a year working with 1 child. Data were collected with work engagement scale, work-life balance scale, and mindfulness scale. AMOS SEM analysis was used to analyze the data. Findings indicate that work life-balance is positively influence to work engagement, while mindfulness is negatively influence to work engagement. The contribution work-life balance with work engagement is 41,8%, and simultaneously effecting work life-balance and mindfulness on work engagement are 17,3%. Work engagement and work life balance working mothers indicate low while mindfulness is high. Most of the subjects are millennial mothers with 1 child, high school education background, and sewer division with regional minimum wage. Connections between high mindfulness and work engagement is not affecting, therefore they consider that work life-balance is essential. Therefore, it is essential for working's mothers to improve capabilities of mindfulness skill at both area as employee and mother to get better work life-balance to increase productivity among millennial working's mothers.

Keywords: *Work Life-Balance, Mindfulness, Work Engagement Of Working Mother.*

INTRODUCTION

Backgrounds

Apparel or garment industry been participating of 7 percent of the nation's exports. A middle-developed country, Indonesia has about 2.2 million citizens employed in the sector; about 83 percent of these workers are women. [1]. One of the TPT companies that been exports 100% of its production come from PT. BRA. Total employees are 8,620 people with 8,203 female employees, of which more than 70% or around 6,034 people are working mothers. A total export in 2021 is around 24 million units with an export value of US\$1,260 million spread across 39 countries [2].

The one of the factory location in Bantul, Yogyakarta which has a higher female population around 479,573 people compared to 476,234 men out of a total population of 955,807 people [3]. The number of female workers in 2021 is 39.52% or 51.79 million, an increase of 1.09 million people from 2020 of 50.7 million people [4]. The percentage of the formal workforce in Indonesia in 2021 will consist of 43.39% male and 36.20% female. Report says the percentage of the population aged 15 years and over with the highest level of tertiary education was 10.06% for women and 9.28% for men [5]. The education level of Indonesian women is higher than that of men. As the education level of women increases, awareness arises that a woman also has the potential to develop and be successful by working.

But, increment women's workers are not meet competitiveness or requirement skill on garment industry. In fact, Indonesia's global competitiveness index ranking in the World Economic Forum (WEF) report in 2018 Indonesia was ranked 45th out of 140 countries, then ranked 36th in 2019 again dropped to rank 50th in 2020, then rose to rank 37th in 2021 and will fall again in 2022 to rank 44. Indonesia's global competitiveness index is relatively low and efforts to increase productivity require the involvement of its employees [6].

A global survey conducted by Gallup illustrates that there are 19% of employees who are actively disengaged, and 21% who are engaged in their work by 2021 [7]. The trend for employees who are actively disengaged has tended to decline since it was recorded in 2009 to 2021, while the trend for engaged workers has experienced an increase in the same timeframe. Gallup also concludes that by 2022 the percentage of employee engagement in the U.S. also slowly decreased since 2020 to 2% [8]. The consequences that can arise from low work engagement for companies include, among others, decreased productivity, delays in completing work, high turnover, low quality of products produced, to poor individual welfare of the employees themselves [9]

Work engagement is a positive paradigm of a worker or attitude, a condition both psychologically, physically or intellectually which is characterized by the first is vigor related to the condition of the size of the energy possessed and high mental immunity when carrying out work, the second is dedication related to participation at work, and third is absorption related to full concentration of mind, so that it can maximize performance and productivity at work in order to achieve goals. [10]

The attachment of working mothers can be a potential in improving the quality of Human Resources Company. [11] The increasing number of women's attachment to the world of work will reduce the time in public affairs compared to the domestic sector, so that more women entering the workforce will reduce the speed of population growth. [12] Working women have contributed to increasing the economic welfare of their families. The role of a woman cannot be ignored anymore in the process of creating better generation, but empowering women can increase the readiness of human resources with their natural characteristics to provide a society that is responsive to social problems or issues. In this case, in the form of social construction at the smallest level, the family can be interpreted as an important step in ensuring the direction of the progress of a nation [13]

Several studies have shown that women's work engagement tends to be low due to several

factors such as research on work engagement and gender conducted by [14] which results that men have higher work engagement because their main position is being the breadwinner in the family, while the position of women is the opposite. Similarly, research conducted by ([15] also explained that gender differences can affect the level of work engagement, the result of which is that men have a higher level of work engagement than women. Then the results of other studies state that engaged men are considered easier to work when compared to women [16] In addition, work engagement is self-expression to do good work that comfortable as a form of cognitive and affective investment that creates a relationship between workers and organizations [27]. Regarding the role of working mothers in the workplace, it is a demand for attachment for organizational effectiveness and productivity, even though it has challenges to maintain work-life balance and family [28]. According to the results of [25] the effect of work-life balance on work engagement, especially for working women, can be seen when work and family conflict among working mothers is high, it will lead to low work engagement, while when work and family conflict is low, work engagement is high. One of the factors for achieving work engagement is that a balance between work and personal life will have an impact on work engagement, so that workers are better able to face every challenge at work and have a quality of life [29]. Work-life balance is defined by [19] who defines not only life balance as previously argued, but rather divides the role of both between psychology and one's life. Work-life balance has various meanings conveyed by several experts, therefore to understand what it really is, it is necessary to study various definitions. Balanced can mean that a person does not have conflicts with the environment, others and himself [30], it is understood that life is balanced when professional duties and personal life coincide. Work-life balance can be interpreted a person in attachment according to personal life and work including other matters, [31]. If a worker feels a balance in their life, they will struggle to maximize professionalism at work [32].

In addition to work-life balance, which has a correlation with the level of work engagement, it is called an internal factor is mindfulness. Mindfulness is obtained from two sides, namely individual attention or awareness as workers and organizations as employers. Organizations must be aware and concerned about skills, knowledge development, ideas and creativity of employees or workers so as to provide all training, yoga and meditation facilities [27]. Meanwhile [21] said workers or employees are actively involved in any activity that mindfulness as an effort to manage emotions and skills and found that attention has a positive impact and a significant correlation with psychological well-being and all aspects are significantly positively correlated with psychological well-being. The concept of mindfulness is associated with psychological well-being [12]

Based on the job demands-resources (JD-R) model, work engagement is predicted by personal capabilities to facing a job demands in the company, job resources, and personal resources. The causes of work-engagement vary and are generally divided into two factors, namely internal and external. Job demands refer to the physical, social, or organizational aspects of a job that require sustained physical and/or psychological effort on the part of the employee. In this case the research subjects are working mothers who work with targets that must be achieved every day or within a certain period of time to determine both their employment status and the compensation received if they reach the target. Job resources, referring to aspects of work that help achieve goals, reduce job demands, and often stimulates personal growth and development such as work-life balance, work family conflict While personal resources are psychological characteristics related to resilience and refer to an individual's ability to control and influence his environment such as resilience, optimism, mindfulness, and perceived control that influence JD-R process through perception and ability to use job resources to deal with job demands. Both of these factors, both external and internal, have a strong impact on work-engagement, however, the researchers focused on internal factors. originating from within and outside the working mother and mindfulness as an internal factor which is a factor from within

the working mother as the interaction of workers and organizations. It is assumed that work engagement is influenced by external and internal factors. [25] defines work-life balance as an ability to commit to family, work, social life and then also be responsible for each of these aspects in a balanced way. Whereas mindfulness is understood as full attention by orienting one's self in the present, by maintaining awareness of one's direct experience without judgmental attitudes [33]. Between work-life balance and mindfulness there is a psychological correlation to work engagement, including for workers, especially working mothers [34].

According to the explanation above, it can be understood that very little research related to work-life balance and mindfulness affecting work engagement is classified as being carried out, especially in Indonesia, including the effect of mindfulness on work engagement [35]. However, throughout this study, there has not been a single study that has one dependent variable and two independent variables, such as the following research title, namely the effect of work-life balance and mindfulness of work engagement in working mothers. This is a novelty as well as a research gap between previous studies.

METHODS

Research Participants

Participants of this study were recruited using a purposive sampling method from female employees at a private garment company in Yogyakarta. The selection criteria were employees who were married, been working at least a year and having at least 1 child in PT.BRA Yogyakarta, Indonesia. We distributed questionnaires with three variables on a paper-based basis to during working hour. Respondents of this study consisted of 533 employees; the majority of them working mothers who were born between 1984 to 1995 [17] (71,1%) and length of work period ranged from 1 months to 5 years (56,4%) with education level, mostly high school(74,1%), sewer division(83,0%) with regional minimum wage(80,5%).

Measurement.

Three scales consisting of work engagement, work life-balance and mindfulness scale were used.. The scales were adapted and been translated from English to Bahasa with good validity and reliability of the scales.

Work Engagement (WE). Work Engagement will be measured using the dimensions of [36] namely: (1) Enthusiasm, characterized by high enthusiasm, mental resilience, endurance at work and having the desire and persistence when meeting working conditions (2) Dedication is a condition marked by a mother's strong attachment to work and always has enthusiasm, pride, inspiration, and challenges at work. (3) Appreciation, characterized as a working mother's condition seen from concentration, happiness and enjoyment of work marked by the emergence of a feeling of difficulty leaving her job. The work engagement was measured using Utrecht Work engagement Scale (UWES 9) a scale developed by [10] and been translated to Bahasa by [18]. Responses range in 4 range scale, from 1 (Strongly suitable) to 4 (Strongly not suitable). Each response's possible score range is 4 till 16. A higher score on the scale shows a higher level of work engagement. Work engagement scale has good reliability ($\alpha = .822$) and discrimination index (.527-.647).

Work Life-Balance (WLB). Work-life balance will be measured using the dimensions [19] namely: (1) WIPL, the extent to which work can interfere with the life of working mothers (2) PLIW, the extent to which working mothers interfere with work life. (3) WEPL, the extent to which work can increase the quality of life of working mothers. (4) PLEW, the extent to which a working mother's life is able to increase performance. The work life-balance was measured using a scale developed by [19] Journal of Occupational Health Psychology 2009, Vol. 14, No. 4 , 441–456) consist 17 item and it been translated to Bahasa by [20] Responses range in 17 range scale, from 1 (Strongly suitable) to 4 (Strongly not suitable). Each response's possible score range is 4 till 68. A higher score on the scale shows a low level of work life-balance.

Work life-balance scale has good reliability ($\alpha = .903$) and discrimination index (.787-.961).

Mindfulness (MD). Researchers use the concept of mindfulness described by [21] with five aspects, namely observing, describing, behaving in a conscious way, not judging what is thought or felt, not responding to what is thought or felt. This attitude will make good thoughts and attitudes reflect with a scientific view resulting in an individual's meaning of all events or stimuli that appear to be wider and more fully accepted. If someone has reached this point, it will help in carrying out their roles and responsibilities. The mindfulness was measured using Five Facet Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ) developed by [21] consist 38 item and been translated to Bahasa by [22] Responses range in 4 range scale, from 1 (Strongly suitable) to 4 (Strongly not suitable). There were 13 items dropped during trial research and final mindfulness scale consist 25 items. Each response's possible score range is 25 till 100. A higher score on the scale shows a low level of mindfulness. Mindfulness scale has good reliability ($\alpha = .955$) and discrimination index (.802-.979).

Data Analysis

SEM-AMOS technique was used to test the hypothesis, due to big no of sample research and data is not normally distributed and 127 outlier been dropped to achieve normally distributed. Moreover, SEM-AMOS was chosen for this study due to its ability to perform better when the objective is a prediction, and the phenomenon is relatively new or changing. Using AMOS, one can estimate, specify and access their model in the form of a diagram and define the relationship between the variables. AMOS also allows building models that reflect the relationships with the capability to use variables. With AMOS, one can perform statistical estimation, which allows the users to – create multiple modification models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The highest numbers of respondents are working mothers who have work engagement and work-life balance which are classified as low while mindfulness is classified as high. Hypothesis testing was conducted to determine the influence of work life-balance and mindfulness to work engagement of working mothers in the garment company PT. BRA. In order to analyse data for all paths were generated using SEM-AMOS. The measurement results of all paths are shown in Figure 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1. Result of the SEM-AMOS analysis

The final result of the goodness of fit index value parameter, all the goodness of fit parameter results are classified as good except for the Sig Probability the result is 0.025 or <0.05 because MI has an error and there are cross variables which affecting if correlated will interfere with the prediction of the independent variable to the dependent variable, so that it can be said that the model results is fit or acceptable. [23] explained that convergent validity at AMOS is shown with Average Variance Extracted (AVE) which is meant as a degree to which latent construct explains the variance of its indicators with minimum AVE > .5. The results indicators variance regression weight reflected the latent construct such as work engagement WE1 represent Vigor is 0.44 mean >.5.

Table 1 *Path Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing*

Hypothesis	Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Conclusion
H ₁	WLB → WE	.194	.039	4.929	***	Supported
H ₂	MD → WE	.010	.011	.948	.343	Not Supported
H ₃	WLB & MD → WE	7.195	.427	16.846	***	Supported

Discussion

This research reported that work life-balance and mindfulness have a significant affecting with work engagement. The affecting between work life-balance and mindfulness to work engagement is categorized as substantial. The meaning of substantial that will have a low productivity if they get low work life-balance and high mindfulness are simultaneously not affecting work engagement. The work engagement influenced by work life-balance and mindfulness (17.30%).

Work engagement for working's mom in garment industry relate to a target work system is a very influential criterion for the ability to maintain work-life balance. A good work-life balance for working mothers will have an impact on increasing work engagement even with high work demands [24]

First hypothesis on the results of this study is reinforced by the opinion [25] that employees who have a good work-life balance are able to maintain their personal life so that it does not interfere with their work life. Taking care of the household and children is indeed the mother's job when at home. When women decide to work, they must be able to complete tasks at home properly. If there is a conflict with the husband at home it should be resolved immediately so as not to reduce or interfere with the working mother's performance. This is also in accordance to opinion [26] which states that work-life balance in career women who have multiple roles finds that the imbalance between work and family life is caused by personality factors with the discovery of professionalism, responsibility, and feelings of easy change that make the subject prioritize work. Attitudes that prioritize work can cause stress and conflict in the household. The difficulty factor in dividing multiple roles also causes problems. Based on this, it is clear that work-life balance can actually be obtained if career women are able to divide their time and roles. If you're working do it seriously. Likewise when you are at home, quality time with your family is still being carried out so that children will always feel loved, a mother who works while at home must be able to provide warmth to her child so that her attachment to her child is maintained.

Work engagement as describing attitudes related to the physical, cognitive, and emotional dimensions of an employee to be willing to work with full responsibility that comes from within the employee [25]. This requires an aspect of self-evaluation that is positively related to individual mindfulness of one's own ability to control and influence every action that will be taken around him [39]. [37] Found that mindfulness affects focusing on what is happening, so that one is able to see what resources one can use to solve the demands one is facing. Mindfulness will also filter out demands to separate oneself from work experience and the

emotions it experiences.

The rejection of the hypothesis in the results of this study is different from the results of previous studies, one of which is research from [40] which shows a significant relationship between mindfulness and work engagement. There is previous research been supported and shows that not all aspects of work engagement are related to mindfulness. [38] found in the results of research on employees from various sectors in Lithuania that mindfulness was only significantly related to enthusiasm and dedication, then after conducting a regression analysis there was no significant effect of mindfulness on and work engagement. [35] Examined 651 employees in Tilburg, The Netherlands, found that in the JD-R model there is no significant relationship between mindfulness and work engagement, but mindfulness is related to and affects burnout in a separate model.

Although the FFMQ measurement tool has previously been used to measure mindfulness of employees and produces a positive correlation between mindfulness and work engagement by [35] the employee's attitude towards his work influences, for example, when an employee has a job full of pressure, a high level of mindfulness can make employees more aware of negative feelings that can cause anxiety and discomfort at work [38]. This reason is supported by other research which shows that mindfulness does not always have a positive impact, there are individual differences that affect the impact on how individuals respond to awareness. Several experimental results show that mindfulness interventions can also mediate increased anxiety, stress and depression [41]

Refer to [42] mindfulness contributes positively to each dimension of psychological well-being significantly and awareness of life can increase positive emotions, increase harmony of well-being.

CONCLUSION

There is an effect of work-life balance on work attachment to working mothers. However, there is no mindfulness effect on work attachment to working mothers. There is a concurrent influence between work-life balance and mindfulness of work engagement in working mothers.

The effective contribution of work-life balance and mindfulness in predicting work engagement is 17,3% while the remaining 82.7% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study, such as job satisfaction, calling-meaning of work, denial, resilience and perceived organizational support.

Working mothers not only involve cognitive abilities in carrying out multiple roles, working mothers are able to regulate behaviour and social systems that will be formed and skills so that role conflicts do not occur, in this case the working mother's attachment will be formed if the mother works individual ability in balancing between work and private life, cognitive abilities and as part of an organizational system as well as mindfulness as self-ability in managing emotional awareness in dealing with every situation encountered both in the work and family environment. Working mothers not only involve cognitive abilities in carrying out multiple roles, working mothers are able to regulate behaviour and social systems that will be formed and skills so that role conflicts do not occur, in this case the working mother's attachment will be formed if the mother works individual ability in balancing between work and private life, cognitive abilities and as part of an organizational system as well as mindfulness as self-ability in managing emotional awareness in dealing with every situation encountered both in the work and family environment.

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